

NOVEL TRI PHASIC BIOACTIVE COLLAGEN-CHITOSAN-NANOHYDROXYAPATITE MEMBRANE IN TREATING INTRABONY DEFECT (A RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIAL)

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Abstract

Objective: The aim of this study is to evaluate clinically and radiographically the effects of Collagen-Chitosan-Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane in treatment of periodontal intrabony defects. **Materials & Methods:** Thirty-six patients participated in this study. Patients were divided into three groups. Group I, twelve patients received open flap debridement only, group II, twelve patients received open flap debridement with collagen, chitosan & nanohydroxyapatite membrane, group III, twelve patients received open flap debridement with collagen type I membrane. Data were obtained from the three groups at baseline, 3 months and 6 months regarding Plaque index (PI), Modified sulcular bleeding index (MS), Probing depth (PD), Clinical attachment level (CAL) and radiographic measurements were statistically analyzed and compared. **Results:** There were no significant difference in PI or MS or CAL at baseline, at 3 months and at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in PD at baseline and at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in PD between group I and II at 3 months ($p = 0.74$). There was a significant decrease in PD of group I compared with that of group III at 3 months ($p = 0.04$). There was a significant decrease in PD of group II compared with that of group III at 3 months ($p = 0.002$). **Conclusion:** From the results of the present study, we can conclude that Collagen-Chitosan-Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane Improve the clinical Attachment level and pocket depth.

Keywords: Open Flap Debridement, Chitosan, Collagen, Intrabony Defect, Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is an inflammatory disease affecting the supporting tissues of the teeth. In the presence of risk factors, it is a multi-factorial and multi-etiological infectious disease process induced by periodontal bacteria and the host immunological response ¹.

Periodontal tissue degeneration can be reduced by removing pathogenic biofilms and suppressing inflammation. However, the ability to restore lost tissues is dependent on multiple factors, including the extent of tissue defect, overall health, and age ².

Periodontal therapy relies heavily on scaling and root planing (SRP). Its main objective is to remove both soft and hard microbial residues from the diseased root surfaces. It reduces clinical inflammation and pocket probing depth remarkably well ³.

However, the efficacy of SRP can be restricted because it is incapable of completely eradicating all bacteria in cases with deep pocket, root concavities, grooves, furcation involvement, and invasion of root surface abnormalities ⁴.

In order to overcome this limitation other treatment modalities began to gain traction as supplementary to mechanical procedures. Pharmacological disinfectants and antibiotics as adjuncts to SRP may facilitate resolution of the inflammation ⁵.

However, Because of the risk of bacterial resistance and the effect on the entire microbiota composition of the human organism that is deeply connected to systemic antibiotic administration, antibiotic use must be critically questioned, especially in terms of its potential added benefit and adverse side effects for the patient ⁶.

Different studies have suggested that Guided bone regeneration (GTR) is an effective treatment modality for the management of intrabony defects (IBD). GTR was associated with the shallowest remaining defects and the best results in improving Clinical attachment Level (CAL) gain, reducing Pocket depth (PD), less increase in gingival recession and more gain in hard tissue probing at re-entry surgery when compared to open flap debridement or the use of bone grafts alone ⁷.

On the other hand, bone grafting procedures have been advocated for the reconstruction of the lost supporting apparatus through the following mechanisms; osteoinduction, osteoconduction, and osteoneogenesis. Bone grafts used include autografts, allografts, xenografts and alloplasts ⁸.

For enhanced periodontal regeneration, delivery of growth factors in the local environment holds a great deal either used alone or in adjunct to other materials such as bone grafts ⁹.

In vitro study reported that chitosan/nano-hydroxyapatite has osteoconductive effect which is proved by the increased osteocalcin expression. Several studies reported that it is a promising clinical alternative to autografts and allografts for bone grafting procedures ¹⁰.

This study has been conducted to evaluate the clinical effects of Chitosan, nanohydroxyapatite and collagen membrane in treatment of periodontal intrabony defects.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present randomized controlled study included 36 patients aged from 25 to 55 years selected from the outpatient clinic of Oral Medicine and Periodontology Department, Faculty of Dentistry, October 6 University with stage II and III periodontitis and their own written informed consent of participation in the study. Screening of patients was continued until the target sample was achieved.

The study protocol was approved by the ethic committee of scientific research faculty of dentistry, October 6 University Egypt, with approval number: RECO6U/26-2022 obtained in its meeting held on November 12, 2022. All subjects participated in this study signed a written consent and fully agreed to participate in this work.

Inclusion criteria involved Patient having stage II and III periodontitis with probing pocket depths ≥ 5 mm and radiographic evidence showing intrabony defect, Patients with Grade B periodontitis, systemically healthy individuals. Patient with probing depth more than 5 mm after phase 1 therapy, pocket depth is measured and if more than 5 mm, the surgery will be done ¹¹ And Compliant patients willing follow oral hygiene instructions. While Exclusion criteria were Patients received periodontal or antibiotic therapy within the previous 6 months preceding the study ¹², somking, Pregnant and lactating females or Patients on medications known to affect bone turnover.

Considering that percentage of clinical attachment Level is the primary objective and based on the data indicating that standard deviation (SD) of the differences in the paired measurements would not surpass 30%, the sample size for paired continuous data were calculated (80% power which is equal $\beta = 0.20$ type II error level with 5% type I error level which is equal $\alpha = 0.05$ probability level). This provided 80% power to disclose a true difference of 20% points between test and control. Statistical analysis showed that each group should be formed at least from 18 patients.

A sample size of 36 (12in each group) was calculated using G Power with the power 80 and α error 0.05 based on the study done by Babrawala et a 2019.¹³ The sample size calculation was performed considering 80% power, 5% significance level, and 1.0 as standard deviation, 12 patients per group were needed. GPower was used for sample size calculation (University of Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf, Germany).

Patients were fully informed about the steps of this study. After initial examination all patients were motivated to perform personal oral hygiene measures using soft toothbrush and interdental cleansing devices. Each patient received full mouth supra and sub-gingival debridement. The patients were divided into three groups as follows. Patients were randomly assigned into three groups: GROUP I: open flap debridement only, GROUP II: (test group): open flap debridement with Collagen-Chitosan-

Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane and GROUP III: open flap debridement with collagen membrane.

Participants were blinded and randomly assigned using a computer-generated list of random numbers. Either to test or control group. Allocation was performed in blocks of 4 by a trial independent individual and the allocation ratio was intended to be equal.

The used Materials are Collagen type I and Chitosan was purchased with low molecular weight (50.000 to 100.000 u) and degree of de-acetylation (DD 75 %). Preparation of nano-Hap;500 ml of 0.4 mol of diammonium hydrogen phosphate with pH-4.0 was vigorously stirred in 2 L beaker at room temperature and 500 mL of 0.6 mol calcium nitrate tetrahydrate with pH=7.4 was added drop-wise over 4 h. The pH of the system was maintained at 10.8 throughout the stirring process, by using 0.1 M sodium hydroxide. The mixture was allowed to remain stirred overnight. A white precipitate was formed. The precipitate was vacuum dried and cleaned with distilled water and ethanol simultaneously for three or four times. The prepared powder was used for further characterization ¹⁴. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Nano-HAP Preparation by Wet Chemical Method

Surgical procedures:

All teeth, with intrabony pockets ≥ 5 mm in the same quadrant as the teeth selected to the study, were surgically treated. In all locations, under local anesthesia, an intracrevicular incision, full-thickness muco-periosteal flaps were reflected Surface of

roots were scaled and planed only as Group I, but we put collagen, chitosan & nanohydroxyapatite membrane in the defect as Group II, additionally we put collagen membrane in the defect as Group III. Then an interrupted suture of the flap.

Method of Clinical Evaluation:

The following clinical parameters measurements were evaluated for every patient included in present study before and after surgery at base, 3 and 6 months.

1. Modified sulcular bleeding index (MS).
2. Plaque index (PI).
3. Clinical attachment level.
4. Pocket depth (PD).
5. Radiographic Examination: radiographic measurements were performed at baseline and 6 months. Radiographs taken using Digital periapical X-ray using image plate and dental X-ray machine set at 70 KVP, 8 mA and 0.08 - 0.04 s. The intraoral radiograph was captured using paralleling technique with film.

Statistical analysis was done by SPSS v26 (IBM Inc., Armonk, NY, USA). Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD), the two groups were compared utilizing unpaired Student's t- test and compared between different readings utilizing ANOVA (F) test. Qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage (%) and were analyzed utilizing the Chi-square test. A two tailed P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Thirty-six patients participated in this study. Patients were divided into three groups. Group I, twelve patients received open flap debridement, group II, twelve patients received open flap debridement, Chitosan, nano-hydroxyapatite, group III, twelve patients received open flap debridement, collagen type I membrane.

Data were obtained from the three groups at baseline, 3 months and 6 months regarding Plaque index (PI), Modified sulcular bleeding index (MS), probing depth (PD), Clinical attachment level (CAL) and radiographic measurements were statistically analyzed and compared. Mixed ANOVA was conducted to investigate the effect of treatment on PI, MS, PD, CAL and radiographic measurements.

I- Plaque Index:

Group I

The mean \pm SD PI of group I at baseline was 1.83 ± 0.75 , and at 3 months was 1.17 ± 0.75 and at 6 months was 0.67 ± 0.82 . The mean difference in PI between baseline and 3 months was 0.66. There was no significant difference in PI between baseline and 3 months ($p = 0.14$). The mean difference in PI between baseline and 6 months was 1.16. There was a significant decrease in PI at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p =$

0.005). The mean difference in PI between 3 months and 6 months was 0.5. There was no significant difference in PI between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 0.21$). (Figure 2).

Group II

The mean \pm SD PI of group II at baseline was 2.17 ± 0.58 , and at 3 months was 0.92 ± 0.09 and at 6 months was 0.25 ± 0.62 . The mean difference in PI between baseline and 3 months was 1.25. There was a significant decrease in PI at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PI between baseline and 6 months was 1.92. There was a significant decrease in PI at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PI between 3 months and 6 months was 0.67. There was a significant decrease in PI at 6 months compared with that at 3 months ($p = 0.005$). (Figure 2).

Group III

The mean \pm SD PI of group III at baseline was 2.20 ± 0.92 , and at 3 months was 1.00 ± 1.05 and at 6 months was 0.60 ± 1.07 . The mean difference in PI between baseline and 3 months was 1.2. There was a significant decrease in PI at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PI between baseline and 6 months was 1.6. There was a significant decrease in PI at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PI between 3 months and 6 months was 0.4. There was no significant difference in PI between 3 and 6 months ($p = 0.19$). (Figure 2).

Comparison between Groups

There was no significant difference in PI at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in PI at 3 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in PI at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Mean PI at baseline, 3 months and 6 months of group I, II, and III

II- Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index:

Group I

The mean \pm SD MS of group I at baseline was 1.67 ± 0.52 , and at 3 months was 1.17 ± 0.75 and at 6 months was 0.83 ± 0.75 . The mean difference in MS between baseline and 3 months was 0.5. There was no significant difference in MS between baseline and 3 months ($p = 0.14$). The mean difference in MS between baseline and 6 months was 0.84. There was a significant decrease in MS at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.01$). The mean difference in MS between 3 months and 6 months was 0.34. There was no significant difference in MS between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 0.25$). (Figure 3).

Group II

The mean \pm SD MS of group II at baseline was 1.92 ± 0.67 , and at 3 months was 0.67 ± 0.49 and at 6 months was 0.25 ± 0.45 . The mean difference in MS between baseline and 3 months was 1.25. There was a significant decrease in MS at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in MS between baseline and 6 months was 1.67. There was a significant decrease in MS at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in MS between 3 months and 6 months was 0.42. There was a significant decrease in MS at 6 months compared with that at 3 months ($p = 0.01$). (Figure 3).

Group III

The mean \pm SD MS of group III at baseline was 2.00 ± 0.82 , and at 3 months was 0.90 ± 0.88 and at 6 months was 0.80 ± 0.79 . The mean difference in MS between baseline and 3 months was 1.1. There was a significant decrease in MS at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in MS between baseline and 6 months was 1.2. There was a significant decrease in MS at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in MS between 3 months and 6 months was 0.1. There was no significant difference in MS between 3 and 6 months ($p = 1$). (Figure 3).

Comparison between Groups

There was no significant difference in MS at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in MS at 3 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in MS at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mean MS at baseline, 3 months and 6 months of group I, II, and III

III- Periodontal Probing Depth:

Group I

The mean \pm SD PD of group I at baseline was 7.50 ± 2.81 , and at 3 months was 3.50 ± 0.55 and at 6 months was 3.17 ± 0.41 . The mean difference in PD between baseline and 3 months was 4. There was a significant decrease in PD at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.002$). The mean difference in PD between baseline and 6 months was 4.33. There was a significant decrease in PD at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PD between 3 months and 6 months was 0.33. There was no significant difference in PD between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 0.25$). (Figure 4).

Group II

The mean \pm SD PD of group II at baseline was 7.01 ± 2.50 , and at 3 months was 3.25 ± 0.72 and at 6 months was 3.21 ± 0.72 . The mean difference in PD between baseline and 3 months was 3.76. There was a significant decrease in PD at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PD between baseline and 6 months was 3.8. There was a significant decrease in PD at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in PD between 3 months and 6 months was 0.04. There was no significant difference in PD between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 1$). (Figure 4).

Group III

The mean \pm SD PD of group III at baseline was 6.85 ± 1.63 , and at 3 months was 4.40 ± 0.70 and at 6 months was 3.70 ± 0.92 . The mean difference in PD between baseline and 3 months was 2.45. There was a significant decrease in PD at 3 months compared with

that at baseline ($p = 0.01$). The mean difference in PD between baseline and 6 months was 3.15. There was a significant decrease in PD at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.002$). The mean difference in PD between 3 months and 6 months were 0.7. There was a significant decrease in PD at 6 months compared with that at 3 months ($p = 0.001$). (Figure 4).

Comparison between Groups

There was no significant difference in PD at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in PD between group I and II at 3 months ($p = 0.74$). There was a significant decrease in PD of group I compared with that of group III at 3 months ($p = 0.04$). There was a significant decrease in PD of group B compared with that of group III at 3 months ($p = 0.002$). There was no significant difference in PD at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Mean PD at baseline, 3 months and 6 months of group I, II, and III

IV- Clinical Attachment Level:

Group I

The mean \pm SD CAL of group I at baseline was 6.08 ± 0.53 , and at 3 months was 4.18 ± 1.31 and at 6 months was 3.85 ± 1.46 . The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 3 months was 1.9. There was no significant difference in CAL between baseline and 3 months ($p = 0.16$). The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 6 months was 2.23. There was no significant difference in CAL between baseline and 6 months ($p = 0.13$). The mean difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months was 0.33. There was no significant difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 0.24$). (Figure 5).

Group II

The mean \pm SD CAL of group II at baseline was 7.63 ± 2.96 , and at 3 months was 3.63 ± 1.07 and at 6 months was 3.38 ± 1.03 . The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 3 months was 4. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 6 months was 4.25. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.001$). The mean difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months were 0.25. There was no significant difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months ($p = 0.19$). (Figure 5).

Group III

The mean \pm SD CAL of group III at baseline was 7.00 ± 1.97 , and at 3 months was 4.40 ± 0.74 and at 6 months was 3.80 ± 0.67 . The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 3 months was 2.6. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.004$). The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 6 months were 3.2. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.002$). The mean difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months were 0.6. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 6 months compared with that at 3 months ($p = 0.001$). (Figure 5).

Comparison between Groups

There was no significant difference in CAL at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in CAL at 3 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in CAL at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Mean CAL at baseline, 3 months and 6 months of group I, II, and III

V- Radiographic Evaluation:

The mean \pm SD radiographic measurements of group I at baseline was 6.67 ± 1.32 , The mean \pm SD radiographic measurements of group II at baseline was 6.95 ± 1.77 , The mean \pm SD radiographic measurements of group III at baseline was 7.12 ± 1.66 . (Table 2).

Table 1: Group I, Group II and Group III at base line

Radiographic measurements (mm)			
	Group I	Group II	Group III
	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	$\bar{X} \pm SD$
Baseline	6.67 ± 1.32	6.95 ± 1.77	7.12 ± 1.66
3 months	6.62 ± 1.21	6.68 ± 1.66	6.91 ± 1.47
6 months	6.61 ± 1.20	4.95 ± 0.92	6.27 ± 1.24

The mean difference in radiographic measurements of group I between baseline and 3 months was 0.05. There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements between baseline and 3 months ($p = 1$). The mean difference in radiographic measurements of group II between baseline and 3 months was 0.27. There was a significant decrease in radiographic measurements at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.01$). The mean difference in radiographic measurements between baseline and 3 months was 0.21. There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements between baseline and 3 months ($p = 0.11$). The mean difference in radiographic measurements of group I between baseline and 6 months was 0.06. There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements between baseline and 6 months ($p = 1$) (Table 3).

Table 2: Comparison between groups

Between group comparison				
		MD	p- value	Sig
Baseline	Group I vs II	-0.28	0.94	NS
	Group I vs III	-0.45	0.86	NS
	Group II vs III	-0.17	0.96	NS
3 months	Group I vs II	-0.06	0.99	NS
	Group I vs III	-0.29	0.92	NS
	Group II vs III	-0.23	0.93	NS
6 months	Group I vs II	1.66	0.01	S
	Group I vs III	0.34	0.82	NS
	Group II vs III	-1.32	0.02	S

There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements at 3 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). There was a significant

decrease in radiographic measurements of group II compared with that of group I at 6 months ($p = 0.01$). There was a significant decrease in radiographic measurements of group II compared with that of group C at 6 months ($p = 0.02$). There was no significant difference in radiographic measurements at 6 months between group I and III ($p = 0.82$). (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Mean radiographic measurements at baseline, 3 months and 6 months of group I, II, and III

DISCUSSION

Periodontitis is an inflammatory disease affecting the supporting tissues of the teeth. It is a multi-factorial and multi-etiological infectious disease process induced by periodontal bacteria and the host immunological response¹⁵. The main aim of periodontal therapy is to improve the gingival health of the patient and preserve the remaining periodontal tissues.¹⁶ Treatment modalities of periodontitis include materials derived from the nature, have been shown to yield faster healing. In the current study, Collagen- Chitosan-Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane and collagen membrane are used in treatment of periodontal intrabony defects.¹⁷

The current study showed an improvement in MS, PD, and CAL in agreement with the previous study Pradeep AR et al 2015, which reported the effect of scaling and root planning in treatment of intrabony defect. This may be due to the use of 1.2% rosuvastatin and 1% metformin gel which was effective in treatment of intrabony defect.¹⁸

Moreover, the present study revealed that, there were no significant difference in CAL at baseline or after 3 or 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$), in agreement with other study may be the same time of follow up.¹⁹ On the contrary with this present finding

other study Bandeira et al 2017, showed significant difference in CAL at baseline, at 3 months and 6 months between the three groups ($p < 0.05$) and revealed that the combined use of nano-hydroxyapatite and chitosan may have synergistic effect resulting in a more favorable clinical response, and increase bone mass using chitosan alone. This previous study gave 12 month follow up that may cause superior result than our study which tracked 6 month follow up.²⁰ Correspondingly, another research by Vasundhra Ajay Bhardwaj et al 2018 contradicting our study showed significant difference in CAL of 4.37 mm PD reduction and 3.08 mm CAL gain 12 months after using zinc-incorporated nano-HA.²¹

Besides, the mean difference in CAL between baseline and 3 months was 2.6. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 3 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.004$). The mean difference in CAL between baseline and 6 months were 3.2. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 6 months compared with that at baseline ($p = 0.002$). The mean difference in CAL between 3 months and 6 months were 0.6. There was a significant decrease in CAL at 6 months compared with that at 3 months ($p = 0.001$).²²

Supporting our study, Shruthi Eshwar et al 2023 observes reported mean CAL gain of 3.3 mm in a group treated by collagen membrane combined with bovine bone. These findings were similar with present study that revealing the mean \pm SD CAL at baseline was 7.00 ± 1.97 , and at 3 months was 4.40 ± 0.74 and at 6 months was 3.80 ± 0.67 but there were superior results than present study. This can be due to the use bovine bone combined with collagen membrane in the previous study.²³

Additional study Ghousia Fatima et al 2015, demonstrated the beneficial effects of an anorganic bovine-derived hydroxyapatite matrix/cell-binding peptide graft, in terms of CAL gain and PD reduction which in contrast with present study.²⁴

Respectively, regarding the (PD), the current study demonstrated no significant difference in PD at baseline and at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$), which disagree with the Mohammad Abdul Baseer et al 2015, which revealed a significant difference in PD at baseline between the three groups ($p < 0.001$).²⁵

Likewise in agreement with present study, other study Moradi Haghgoo et al 2023 observed the effect of collagen-chitosan membranes for Intrabony defects that reported that, the difference in probing depth between test group and control group was statistically significant It is Reasonable to nanofibrous scaffolds releasing tetracycline hydrochloride which give superior effect in egeneration.²⁶

Other study M L Prabhuji et al, 2019. Showed a reduction in probing depth with 15% chitosan gel for open flap debridement. The outcomes at 6 months showed a PD reduction of 3.8mm for 15%chitosan which is superior due to concentration of chitosan which in present study is 2%.²⁷ Recently study, Sana Hashemi et al 2023 reported the effect of collagen membrane in treatment of intrabony pocket they observed a Statically significant difference in the mean pocket depth (PD), mean CAL, and Defect distance frombaseline to 6 months in group I and group II but there were no statically significant difference in mean PD reduction (0.35 ± 1.90 mm), mean CAL gain (0.28 ± 1.85 mm) and

Defect Distance reduction (0.12 ± 1.42 mm) seen at 6 months when compared between both the groups which is similar to present study that showed The mean \pm SD PD at baseline was 6.85 ± 1.63 , and at 3 months was 4.40 ± 0.70 and at 6 months was 3.70 ± 0.92 .²⁸ As regard to plaque index score recorded in the present study investigation, the results showed that there was a significant difference in the all three group at 3- and 6-months observation period when compared to baseline. This was clarified in a study conducted on hydroxyapatite Indumathy Pandiyan et al, 2022. Which showed antimicrobial activity against various gram-negative and grampositive bacteria.²⁹ there was no significant difference in PI at baseline between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). Further, there were no significant difference in PI at 3 & 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$). Results obtained from the present study of (PI), in group I revealed no significant difference PI in at baseline, at 3 months and at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$), which is similar to other study Archana Vilasan et al 2020, might be to excellent patient motivation protocol and good oral hygiene measure at base, 3, and 6 months.³⁰

Concerning (MS), present study detected we observed that, there were no significant difference in MS at baseline, at 3 months and at 6 months between the three groups ($p > 0.05$), in agreement with other study made by Raveesha R et al, 2022. And this could be due to excellent patient motivation protocol and good oral hygiene measure at base, 3, and 6 months.³¹

CONCLUSION

We were able to conclude the Collagen-Chitosan-Nanohydroxyapatite Membrane Improve the clinical Attachment level and pocket Depth. We recommended that Clinical effects of different chitosan & nano-HAP concentrations are required to be investigated in more studies.

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